

APPLICATION OF EDUCATIONAL EDUCATION IN THE TRUMPET CLASS

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Annotation: The article considers educational training as a methodological basis for the formation of beginner trumpeters. Variants of approaches to the application of the studied phenomenon in the pipe class are shown. Attention is drawn to the educational and teaching dominants, the relationship of which allows for a breakthrough, an effective leap in the training of young musicians. The idea is emphasized that teaching, educating, educating, teaching are important pedagogical formulas of the musical and educational process in the trumpet class.

Key words: nurturing education, student-trumpeter, teacher of the trumpet class, musical and educational process, trumpet, education, training.

Since ancient times, thinkers, philosophers of East and West, aware of the importance of the process of cognition, drew attention to the need for training and education of the younger generation. Confucius stated: "When a noble teacher teaches and instructs, he leads, but does not pull; encourages, but does not force; opens the way, but does not complete it. This gives agreement between the student and the teacher, ease of learning, independent reflection" (Anthology of Wisdom, 2005: 622). At one time, Aristotle understood that "the fate of empires depends on the education of youth" (Anthology of Wisdom, 2005: 623). Lao Tzu made a revelation: "You can know others by yourself; by one kingdom one can know others, by one country one can know the universe" (Anthology of Wisdom, 2005: 618). Jean Jacques Rousseau shared the following: "The surest way to make your child unhappy is to teach him not to meet with anything. You will never be able to create wise men if you kill naughty children" (Anthology of Wisdom, 2005: 627).

Modern modernization of the musical educational system provides for the deepening of the processes of training, upbringing, and education. In this regard, each component of the above triad is filled with new content and receives organizational support.

How to combine training with education, to make these processes optimal and holistic, organically complementing each other? How to solve problems of educational and training character? What is the algorithm of pedagogical actions

that allow effective training and education in the class of wind instruments (one of the most ancient), in particular, trumpet students?

These issues are waiting for their prompt resolution, are the subject of study for many instrumental performers, teachers of the trumpet class.

Therefore, in the pedagogy of musical and instrumental.

Today, the concept of “educational education” is being sufficiently updated in the performance of today. Accumulating in itself two important directions of the educational process, it allows you to move on to understanding, considering the relevant connections, dominants, incentives, motivations, etc.

“Educational education is education, in which an organic connection is achieved between students acquiring knowledge, skills, assimilation of the experience of creative activity and the formation of their personal qualities (worldview, moral and value attitude to the world, each other, digestible educational material, etc.). Educational education is a didactic principle reflected in the content, organizational forms and methods of education” (Rapatsevich, 2006: 98).

Many researchers take a position that reflects the dominant teaching in the musical and educational process of trumpeters. So, E.A. Savin drew attention to the scrupulousness of the formation of breathing technique, embouchure, coordination of performing actions-movements. Therefore, he argued that in the process of playing the trumpet it is impossible to think, intotone, lead the sound without implementing a detailed approach to the technique of performance, working out a conscious, control-auditory and automated, natural sound presentation, which is combined with an ideal representation of sounds-images (Savin, 2012).

T.A. Dokshitser believed that an important place in the formation of trumpeter students is occupied by education, which opens the way for technical improvement, allows the performer to breathe fully, “ahead of time”, creating space for thoughts and feelings / educational dominant /. (Dokshitser, 2011).

V.V. Tokmakov's point of view fell on the determinant nature of education and upbringing. The researcher argued that, by “growing” into each other, they can provide the formation of an educational environment and a learning platform that will allow high-quality training of trumpet students.”

“The performing process as a multifaceted and multi-element phenomenon, on the one hand, contains a large number of detailed technical and performing specific moments, and on the other hand, it presupposes the unity of the performing apparatus, mind and heart. Misunderstanding is compensated, for example, by obtaining new knowledge (training), inability - by the development

of interest, abilities, motivational readiness (education). In other words, even within the same lesson, the teacher always has options for the successful use of educational and at the same time teaching dominants in order to give an “aftakt” to one or another area of work, while solving the problems of a holistic artistic and pedagogical process in the instrumentalist class. Educating, teaching, teaching, educating - these are the main pedagogical "formulas" of the phenomenon under consideration.

The determinism of education and upbringing in the trumpet class can be considered at the level of formation of the trumpeter's melodic and harmonic ear. The specificity of the trumpet makes it possible to actively develop a variety of melodic ear for performers, including the corresponding technically detailed components. At the same time, harmonic ear is also of great importance for a musician.

When playing in an ensemble, an orchestra, it becomes not only in demand, but extremely necessary, necessary. The purity of intonation, the structure of a group of brass instruments, the whole orchestra, expressive, artistically justified playing are inaccessible in the absence of harmonic hearing. The formation of harmonic ear can be carried out not unilinearly (from the side of only training or education), but “volumetrically”, from two sides, when the formation of orchestral consciousness is nourished by the knowledge of collective performance. The ability to play in an ensemble means hearing yourself and the group separately, yourself in a group, a group in an orchestra. At the same time, timbre, tempo-rhythmic, metro-rhythmic, intonational components are of paramount importance. All this cannot be achieved without the presence in the mind of value orientations, a highly artistic model of sounds-images (attributes of education), which allow one to maintain “order”, purity of harmony, a clear, well-coordinated game of trumpeters in an orchestra (a product of education + training). on the other hand, to think that the trumpet is basically a melodic instrument means not only to impoverish its nature, but also not to understand its orchestral-ensemble essence, not to know its main purpose. Even when a trumpeter plays without accompaniment, his "assistants" are the orchestral consciousness, harmonic ear, and not just melodic. They "pave" the way for expressive playing, in which harmonic turns, the dynamics of the orchestral progenitor, the conceptual nature of the orchestra as a whole become "audible". To form, for example, motivational readiness, which allows a novice trumpet player to enter the teaching and educational environment systematically, with a desire, a soprano recorder is used in the trumpet class, as well as a melody

(keyboard and wind instrument). The introduction of these instruments into the musical and educational process makes it possible to productively solve educational problems along with the tasks of learning. Mastering the recorder and melodics helps to maintain and develop interest in playing wind instruments, gradually form musical taste, abilities (aspects of education) and at the same time gain the necessary knowledge, acquire performing skills (aspects of education). There is a fact of successful application of educational training in the trumpet class with the use of additional instruments (soprano recorder, melody).

O.A. Blok, considering the issues of the determinance of the emotional-sensory and logical-semantic beginnings, comes to the position of applying educative learning, taking into account two dominants (educational and teaching). that the development of the definitions under study "should represent the thesaurus of a holistic musical and educational process. Their deep determinance places responsibility on the shoulders of scientists who are called upon to continue the development of this promising direction, revealing the multifaceted specifics of the mental and emotional, conscious and unconscious in musical and instrumental performance XXI century."

Distortions in the direction of training or education are extremely dangerous, especially for novice trumpeter students with a completely unformed performing apparatus (the product of the teaching dominant) and musical consciousness (the product of the educational dominant). Education without education "kills" interest in classes, leaves young trumpeters without a dream, near, medium and distant prospects in mastering the performing arts. Education without education embodies the musical and educational process without the means of achieving knowledge, the embodiment of musical images, the goal "hanging in the air".

Thus, educative teaching in the trumpet class is not only a methodological principle that largely determines the content, tactics and strategy of the musical educational process. It allows, taking into account the individual and creative nature of students-trumpeters, to gradually advance them along the path of the formation of performing technique, performing skills. The use of educative education in the musical and educational practice of trumpeters suggests the presence of continuity between the knowledge paradigm and the modern competence paradigm. Determinacy of the main components of the musical educational process - the path to success for students of the trumpet class, all instrumentalists in general.

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